

EVALUATION OF PARALLEL PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES/COMPUTING

Sanjar Iskandarov

Urgench Branch of The TUIT named After Muhammad Al-Khwarizmi.

e-mail: sanjariskandarov@gmail.com

Abstract. Nowadays line programming do not support new style of hardware and requirements of time expression. According to all of scientist attention of parallel programming, computing. In this thesis, more explanation of parallel programming languages and shown operation of parallel computing.

Introduction

People are always trying to make programs run faster. One way to do so is to divide the work the program must do into pieces that can be worked on at the same time (on different processors). More formally, creating a parallel program depends on finding independent computations that can be executed simultaneously.

Producing a parallel program generally involves three steps:

1. Developing and debugging a sequential program. For existing programs, this step is already done.
2. Transforming the sequential program into a parallel program.
3. Optimizing the parallel program.

Language of parallel programming are widely all computing systems. There are following parallel computing languages: Linda, Modula-3, NESL, Orca, Phantom and others.

Linda provides four operations for accessing tuple space:

Operation	Action
Out	Places a data tuple in tuple space.
Eval	Creates a live tuple (usually starting new process (es)).
In	Removes a tuple from tuple space.
Rd	Reads the values in a tuple in tuple space, leaving the tuple there.

Linda has several characteristics that set it apart from other parallel programming environments:

1. Linda augments the serial programming language (C or FORTRAN). It does not replace it, nor make it obsolete. In this way, C-Linda and Fortran Linda build on investments in existing programs.
2. Linda parallel programs are portable. C-Linda and Fortran Linda are available on a large number of parallel computer systems,

including shared-memory computers, distributed memory computers, and networks, and with few exceptions, Linda programs written for one machine run without change on another.

3. Linda is easy to use. Conceptually, Linda implements parallelism via a logically global memory (virtual shared memory), called tuple space, and a small number of simple but powerful operations on it. Tuple space and the operations that act on it are easy to understand and quickly mastered. In addition, the C-Linda and Fortran Linda compilers support all of the usual program development features, including compile-time error checking and runtime debugging and visualization [1].

In large programs, it is important to place some structure on collections of procedures and variables, restricting the proliferation of names. Modula-3 programs are structured as collections of modules and interfaces. An interface specifies a set a public facilities: types, variables, constants, and procedures. The interface is a contract between the facilities' developers and their clients. A module implements an interface by supplying private data and bodies for interface procedures. To use an interface, a client must import the interface. Interfaces and modules are stored in different files and compiled separately.

Some type of Modula-3 operations:

ISTYPE (x: Reference; T: Ref Type): BOOLEAN. ISTYPE(x, T) is TRUE if and only if x is a member of T. T must be an object type or traced reference type, and x must be assignable to T.

NARROW (x: Reference; T: Ref Type): T. NARROW(x, T) returns x after checking that x is a member of T. If the check fails, a runtime error occurs. T must be an object type or traced reference type, and x must be assignable to T.

TYPECODE (T: Ref Type): CARDINAL
(r: REFANY) : CARDINAL
(r: UNTRACED ROOT) : CARDINAL

Every object type or traced reference type (including NULL) has an associated integer code. Different types have different codes. The code for a type is constant for any single execution of a program, but may differ for different executions. TYPECODE (T) returns the code for the type T and TYPECODE(r) returns the code for the allocated type of r. It is a static error if T is REFANY or is not an object type or traced reference type and other type of operation can see [2].

NESL fully support nested sequences and nested parallelism –the ability to take a parallel function and apply it over multiple instances in parallel. Nested parallelism is important for implementing algorithms with irregular nested loops (where the inner loop lengths depend on the outer iteration) and for divide-and conquer algorithms. NESL also provides a performance model for calculating the asymptotic performance of a program on various parallel machine models. This is useful for estimating running times of algorithms on actual machines and, when teaching algorithms, for supplying a close correspondence between the code and the theoretical complexity [3].

The most important new ideas behind NESL are:

Nested data parallelism: this feature offers the benefits of data parallelism, concise code that is easy to understand and debug, while being well suited for irregular algorithms, such as algorithms on trees, graphs or sparse matrices.

A language based performance model: this gives a formal way to calculate the work and depth of a program. These measures can be related to running time on parallel machines.

Operation	Action
Dist(a,l)	Distribute value a to sequence of length l
#a	Return length of sequence s
a->i	Read from sequence a based on indices i
Drop(a,n)	Drop first n element of sequence a
Flatten	Flatten nested sequence a
Partition	Partition sequence an into nested sequence
Bottop(a)	Split an into nested sequence

Orca is intended for applications programmers rather than systems programmers. This is reflected in its design goals to provide a simple, easy-to-use language that is type-secure and provides clean semantics. Three example parallel applications in Orca, one of which is described in detail, are discussed. One of the existing implementations, which is based on reliable broadcasting, is described. Performance measurements of this system are given for three parallel applications. The measurements show that significant speedups can be obtained for all three applications.

Phantom is an attempt to remedy this situation by providing an interpreted language and run-time environment that supports flexible, transparent, and secure distribution of both program code and data, while providing enough modern programming language features to support large-scale application development. The interpreter for Phantom is implemented entirely in ANSI C for portability, and may be extended with C procedures using the interpreter's foreign function interface.

In Phantom, a higher-order procedure is stored as a closure containing the code for the procedure as well as an environment that maps free identifiers appearing in the procedure to their corresponding storage locations. These storage locations are, in fact, global location addresses. Using global location addresses in closures gives higher-order procedures an intuitive and secure meaning in a distributed context

Conclusion

In the nutshell, all parallel programming language are direction of machine optimizations. Modern processors are both highly concurrent, with interrupts and such, and parallel, with pipelines and multiple functional units. Languages with implicit parallelism reduce the control that the programmer has over the parallel execution of the program, resulting sometimes in less-than-optimal parallel efficiency. Furthermore, a programmer that writes implicitly parallel code does not need to worry about task division or process communication, focusing instead in the problem that his or her program is intended to solve. Implicit parallelism generally facilitates the design of parallel programs and therefore results in a substantial improvement of programmer productivity.

References

1. Корнеев В.В Параллельные вычислительные системы 1999 й.
2. Nelson, Greg. Systems Programming with Modula-3. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1991.
3. John Greiner. A comparison of data parallel algorithms for connected components. In Proceedings Sixth Annual Symposium on Parallel Algorithms and Architecture, page 16-25. June 1994.
4. Muminov B. B., Kh E. Modelling asynchronous parallel process with Petri net //International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT). – 2019. – Т. 8. – С. 400-405.
5. Muminov B. et al. Localization and Classification of Myocardial Infarction Based on Artificial Neural Network //2020 Information Communication Technologies Conference (ICTC). – IEEE, 2020. – С. 245-249.
6. Muminov B., Vuong L. T. Small-brain neural networks rapidly solve inverse problems with vortex Fourier encoders //arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.07682. – 2020.
7. Muminov B. B., Bekmurodov U. B. IDEF models and innovative system for search data in stochastic information environment //2020 IEEE 14th International Conference on Application of Information and Communication Technologies (AICT). – IEEE, 2020. – С. 1-6.
8. Shodiyev F. Y., Eshboyev E. A., Egamberdiyev E. H. Use of generalized estimates to predict the diseases resistance of wheat varieties //ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 4. – С. 602-610.
9. Egamberdiyev E. the The Use of Neural Networks in Predicting Children’s Creative Ability in Preschool Education //Scientific and technical journal of Karshi State University. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1
10. Muminov B., Dauletov A. Mathematical and Information Model of Electronic Document Management System //2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT). – IEEE, 2021. – С. 01-04.
11. Баходир Мўминов, Адилбек Даулетов ЭЛЕКТРОН ҲУЖЖАТ АЙЛАНИШ ТИЗИМЛАРИНИНГ ТАЪМИНОТЛАРИ // АВРИИТТ-2021. 2021. №. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/elektron-uzhzhatai-lanish-tizimlarining-taminotlari> (дата обращения: 05.04.2022).
12. Б. Б. Мўминов, А. Ю. Даулетов ЭЛЕКТРОН ҲУЖЖАТ АЙЛАНИШ ТИЗИМЛАРИНИНГ ҲАЁТ ДАВРИ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №CSPi conference 3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/elektron-uzhzhatai-ylanish-tizimlarining-ayot-davri> (дата обращения: 05.04.2022).